

THE EFFECT OF LEARNING STYLES ON TEACHING PROCESS

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Annotation: The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of learning styles on education and the teaching processes

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Introduction.

There is no denying that teachers and students differ in a number of ways. Both teachers and students can benefit greatly from understanding more about the different learning styles of their classmates. Learning styles of both students and teachers must be recognized and understood in order to engage students in the active process of learning¹. Both matching and mismatching are possible. It is crucial to research how they are related. The compatibility of learning styles and teaching methods has been the subject of numerous studies. The majority of them state that matching the two has a beneficial effect on pupils' performance while mismatching has the opposite effect. Mismatches, however, might occasionally be advantageous, particularly for pupils of lower levels.

The term "learning styles" in general psychology refers to a person's preferred method of learning, which encompasses the procedure of taking in, analysing, and remembering new knowledge². Language learners' chosen general approach to language acquisition is referred to as their language learning styles in the field of research on second language acquisition. The Student Learning Style Scale, the Learning Style Inventory, the Productivity Environmental Preference Survey, and the Embedded Figures Test are just a few of the broad psychology-based exams used to assess the learning preferences of second- and foreign-language learners. Some of them, such the Perceptual Learning Style Questionnaire, the Perceptual Learning Preferences Survey, the Style Analysis Survey, the Learning Style Questionnaire, and the Learning Channel Preference Checklist, have been created especially for study on second or foreign languages. Language learning styles have been a major area of focus in the study of second language acquisition since it is commonly accepted that they play a substantial role in second language acquisition. Different criteria can be used to define learning styles³.

Researchers' perspectives on the nature of styles vary, much like the definitions of learning styles do. According to Keefe, when students engage with the learning environment, their learning styles tend to be rather constant. Ehrman and Oxford hold that learning styles are

¹ Erden, M. and S. Altun, 2006. Learning Styles. İstanbul: Morpa Culture Publications. ISBN: 9752844863.

² Kaplan, E.J. and D.A. Kies, 1995. Teaching styles and learning styles. J. Instruct. Psychol.

³ Butler, K.A., 1988. Learning and teaching styles In theory and practice. Columbia CT: The Learner's Dimension. ISBN-10: 0945852002

internally based traits that persist despite instructional strategies and learning environments. Learners automatically employ different learning techniques to help them assimilate and comprehend new material. Ehrman and Oxford add that learners can adjust old styles when they start to become conscious of them and that new styles can be learned over time. Learning styles “are not permanently determined at birth,” according to Sternberg.

Different circumstances and stages of life can cause learning styles to vary, and environmental reinforcement can form learning styles. For instance, paying students for using particular learning styles may influence their preferences for those types. Additionally, creating learning activities that are better completed with particular learning styles can influence learners to favour those learning styles. He continues by saying that the formation of learning styles through socializing is tied to one’s value system. Learning styles are not entirely innate and are not fixed, according to Kinsella and Sherak. They discovered that, particularly when students achieve academic success, learners tend to prefer the techniques they are most frequently exposed to, and that learning styles can be reinforced by classroom roles and values. Thus, learning preferences are a reflection of routine methods of knowledge acquisition.

Learning techniques is a different phrase that is frequently used in conjunction with the phrase “learning styles”. Learning strategies are the techniques that students use to complete various learning activities, including meaning negotiation, practice, and review. It can be characterized as a set of techniques for learning or employing a second or foreign language in order to complete a task requiring linguistic knowledge. When it comes to learning a second language, Scarcella and Oxford define strategies as “particular acts, behaviours, stages, approaches - such as seeking out conversation partners or encouraging oneself to take on a different language task - employed by students to better their own learning”. Using context clues to infer a word’s meaning, posing inquiries, and task planning are a few examples of second language learning techniques. Learning techniques and second language learning styles are sometimes related because, according to some second language research, they are both important. Cohen focuses on the connection between language learning techniques and the preferred learning styles of second language learners. He makes the argument that a student who prefers a visual, auditory, or group learning style, for instance, may choose tactics that are in line with those preferences when completing a task. However, it might be challenging to ascertain how preferences for learning style may affect the application of methods, he continues.

Literature has made use of a variety of terminologies, including learning style, cognitive style, sensory preference, and personality types. Some of these names have been used interchangeably on occasion, while others have been separated. “The complicated manner, and circumstances under which, learners most efficiently see, process, store, and recall what they are attempting to learn,” is how learning styles are characterized. Cognitive styles, on the other hand, are described as “an individual’s natural, habitual, and preferred means of receiving, processing, and retaining new information and abilities”. Learning styles and cognitive styles are distinguished by Mortimore. He suggests that learning styles are less constant and are more often evident in terms of the methods that students employ to deal with learning. Conversely, cognitive styles are generally consistent. As a result, learning styles—as opposed to learner preferences—can change over time. As some authors use

cognitive style as a more generic word that incorporates learning styles, it should be highlighted that the distinction between cognitive and learning style is not always evident.

According to Kaplan and Kies, a person's learning style is an innate trait that cannot be easily changed throughout life but can be altered and evolved as a result of experiences. While walking, lying, sitting, chatting, playing, and writing, this has an impact on the person. Actions are taken in accordance with these traits. In addition, determining one's learning type is crucial while learning how to study.

On the basis of the significance of preferences in learning, Grasha created a different model. He defines "learning style" as the sum of students' learning experiences when acquiring knowledge. He believes that knowing yourself better might help you identify your own learning style⁴.

Butler claims that learning style is a generic notion that emphasizes the disparities in learning, much like the quality of an umbrella. Butler claims that learning style is a general idea that emphasizes how every person has a unique approach. This can be shown in the clothing chosen, the music listened to, the colours chosen, and the friends and social circles that the people are a part of. These various distinctive styles aid the person in determining their preferred learning style.

According to Allport, a person's perception, mental process, memory, or approach to problem-solving are considered to constitute their learning style. It is expected that these definitions take cognitive processes into account and that people employ their usual learning methods. In 1930 and again in 1961, Allport employed the style idea in his study of learning styles. He also focused on the unique characteristics of each learner.

After examining how the student viewed the surroundings and engaged with his or her learning environment, Keefe has explained enduring cognitive, affective, and physiological qualities using advanced cognitive processes. He has added that the genetic code, personal growth, and great environmental adaption all have an impact on the person who exhibits the aforementioned style traits. He asserts that learning styles have contextual, affective, and cognitive components.

The Kolb learning style model is based on Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory. The use of experiences in the learning process is explored by experiential learning, which differs from other cognitive learning theories. With this foundation, he has built his studies on Lewin's idea of experience learning. A model of learning styles has been created as a result. According to Kolb, learning is the process of interacting positively with one's social and physical surroundings. He then went on to describe "learning" and set it apart from knowledge. Kolb contends that knowledge is the translation of experience into learning.

When determining learning styles, Dunn R. and Dunn K. took into account a few developmental traits. These are biological and developmental traits that vary from person to person. There are some strategies to tailor training to fit the variances resulting from these biological and personal developmental features. In other words, some pupils learn largely through seeing, while others learn primarily through listening and experiencing.

The key, in the opinion of Dunn R. and Dunn K., is that the teacher must choose the methods for how the pupil will learn.

⁴ Şimşek, A., 2004. Learning Style. In: Individual Differences in Education, Deryakulu, D. and Y. Kuzgun (Eds.) Nobel Publication, Ankara, ISBN: 975-591-610-5,

- A student who needs some alone time will signal this by saying “ssshhh!” or by covering their ears to outside noise or by making a “be quiet!” gesture with their hand. Families should designate a quiet, uncluttered study space for these youngsters. The instructor should be aware that it is impossible to learn in a noisy environment. When deciding where to position such pupils, the teacher should also keep in mind that they shouldn’t be seated in noisy areas;
- Many times, it is not apparent at first that certain pupils are uncomfortable when they enter the classroom. After some time, the teacher should watch to see whether the student favors darkly lit areas, if his or her pupils narrow or they continue to blink, if they shy away from the sun and light, or if they turn away from an open window. It’s equally important to think about the alternative. Students could favor a room with lots of light;
- Some pupils desire a setting in school that is as cosy as their home. For instance, if a student crosses his or her legs while standing on top of a table, leaves their desks or tables messy, or lies down, they most likely prefer an unstructured setting to one that is. Since educational settings are official institutions, this type of behaviour is obviously prohibited. The teacher wouldn’t be able to maintain control of the class if every student conducted themselves informally as they could at home;
- Some of the class members excel at using their visual memories. For instance, if a student closely studies the picture that the teacher drew and focuses far more on the image than the subject, these pupils are probably visual learners;
- A student may prefer to study in the cold if they are continuously moving, grumbling about the heat, or walking around with their coat unbuttoned in the cold. However, if the student complains about the weather or is overdressed, the student does not favour a chilly learning environment. If the person struggles with visual and aural tasks, they are likely kinesthetic;
- Dynamic students are those who frequently move around in their seats, get up from their seats, or beg to leave the classroom;
- If a student chooses materials like a cassette tape or CD player while playing, if he or she is not interested in pictures while reading, if they pay attention to details during conversations, if they remember what they heard, or if they enjoy dialogues when the teacher explains a topic in class, they are probably auditory learners;
- While studying, some students feel the need to snack frequently. They must eat while they are learning. However, some pupils who are quiet and at ease don’t need to consume anything while they are in class.

According to Dunn R. and Dunn K., the aforementioned student profiles are what cause the differences in learning styles. Different kids will choose to study passively through visual and aural means, independently, or simply by listening. Those may occasionally be sufficient for them to succeed academically. However, tactile or kinesthetic students are the ones who want dynamism and prefer to learn alongside their friends, and the reason for their success is tied to the makeup of the learning environment at school.

Because of this, there are numerous strong arguments for why learning styles should be taken into account during the teaching and training process. The following can be used to list and summarize them:

- Knowing a person's preferred method of learning allows for the perception of each person as unique from the others. In other words, the individual will develop a unique learning method. As the brain's perception frequencies vary, people interpret stimuli by using their sensory memories. Age and gender are two criteria that might be used to identify variances. The educational goals will be best served by a teacher who is aware of the different learning preferences of his or her pupils.

Effectiveness is enhanced by understanding the student's preferred method of learning. If the student is learning in a setting that is not conducive to his or her preferred learning style, effectiveness will suffer.

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